

Deliverable 5.4

SUSTAINABILITY STRATEGY: EU FOOD WASTE ASSOCIATIONS

Sustainability strategy: EU FW Associations

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Glossary of terms and acronyms

Acronym/Term	Description
OFLW	Zero Food Loss & Waste
CA	Consortium Agreement
D	Deliverable
D&C	Dissemination and communication
DEP	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
ES	Spain
EU FW	European Food Waste
FWA	Food Waste Association
FLW	Food Loss & Waste
FW	Food Waste
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
R&D	Research & Development
R&I	Research & Innovation
REA	European Research Executive Agency
RTO	Research and Technology Organisations

Executive summary

The CHORIZO project aims to act as a catalyst for systemic change in how food loss and waste (FLW) are understood, addressed, and reduced across the food chain. By linking social norms, consumer behaviour, and decision-making processes of food chain actors, CHORIZO has developed tools, data resources, and recommendations that provide concrete solutions for stakeholders at multiple levels. This document constitutes the deliverable D5.4 Sustainability Strategy: EU Food Waste Associations from WP5 on “Innovation upscaling” and has been prepared by FIAB. The sustainability strategy focuses on EU Food Waste Associations (FWAs), recognizing their role as multipliers capable of embedding project results into upcoming programmes, projects, national initiatives, and industry practices.

The term EU Food Waste Association usually refers to any association, network, or organization within the European Union that focuses on food loss and waste (FLW). These can be NGOs, industry associations, research networks, or expert groups working to reduce FLW.

Our vision is to strengthen the role of FWAs as key enablers in the transition towards zero food waste. By building strong and long-lasting collaborations, the project ensures that its outputs—guides, training materials, behavioural tools, the DataHub, and practice abstracts—do not remain static deliverables, but become active resources shaping the future of food systems in Europe.

To effectively engage with FWAs across the EU, FIAB developed a step-by-step roadmap that outlines an outreach strategy and associated recommendations for how the EU FWA’s can swiftly disseminate the project’s outputs. The roadmap includes: Identify key associations through targeted research, prioritizing them based on relevance and regional impact; Establish relationships to present CHORIZO outputs, aiming to build collaborative relationships; Follow-up to ensure consistent engagement and adaptability throughout the process.

The adoption of CHORIZO outputs by FWAs ensures that knowledge and solutions are diffused across diverse stakeholder groups, from NGOs and food banks to industry representatives and ministries. The top-level recommendations shared are focused on: (I) **Integration of evidence-based behavioural insights** into FWA programmes to improve consumer and business engagement with food waste reduction; (II) **Incorporation of project outputs** (DataHub, capacity building programmes, evaluation of interventions) into the ongoing communication, training, and policy activities of FWAs; (III) **Tailored dissemination approaches** that respect the nature of each association—ranging from direct sharing with members and committees, to uploading content on websites, to embedding results in databases for future use; and (IV) **Promotion of inter-project collaboration** through European networks ensuring synergies with other initiatives.

By leveraging the EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub, FoodDrinkEurope, the EU Platform on FLW, EIP-AGRI, ICLEI, and national ministries, the project’s results reach not only the immediate partners but also a wider European community of practice, and the project ensures lasting influence on European food waste policies, practices, and cultural norms, accelerating progress towards the shared vision of zero food waste.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Project context

The EU and the EU countries are committed to meeting Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) Target 12.3, adopted in September 2015, which aims to halve per capita global food waste at the retail and consumer level by 2030, and reduce food losses along the food production and supply chains. Quantification of European food waste levels (latest estimate by Eurostat, 2022) reveal that 69% of EU food waste arises in the household, food service and retail sectors, with production and processing sectors contributing the remaining 31%.

Tackling food waste means working together with all key players from public and private sectors in order to better identify, measure, understand and find solutions to deal with food waste. There is not one single cause with one solution because the food chain is a complex and dynamic system. All actors in the food chain need to work together to find solutions, from farmers, processors, manufacturers, and retailers to consumers themselves. Policy makers, research scientists, food banks and other NGOs also play an important role¹.

Committed with this SDG explained in the EU Platform on FLW, CHORIZO project adds an innovative initiative based on case studies involving all food chain actors to improve the understanding between social norms, consumer behaviours and economic actor decisions and FLW generation and use this knowledge to improve the effectiveness of decision-making and engagement of food chain actors, towards zero food waste.

The project's main goal is to address existing research gaps and use its outcomes to deliver and advance innovations helping actors to engage more effectively in food waste prevention and reduction activities.

1.2 Project objectives

In this essence, CHORIZO is a project funded by Horizon Europe programme that aims to improve the understanding between social norms, consumer behaviours and economic actor decisions and Food Loss and Waste (FLW) generation and use this knowledge to improve the effectiveness of decision-making and engagement of food chain actors, towards zero food waste. The project's main goal was to address existing research gaps and use its outcomes to deliver and advance innovations, helping relevant actors to be engaged more effectively in food waste prevention and reduction activities. In short, it is a European project that integrates European Commission (EC) and food chain actors to enhance contingency knowledge and produce new effective instruments for facilitating successful transitions towards minimising FLW.

To achieve its aim, the project provided evidence on the role of existing social norms in actors' FLW behaviours through translating results from previous FLW actions into evidence and generate new evidence on social norms & FLW behaviours. Second, CHORIZO embedded these research results into innovation products that foster change of FLW-related social norms. These products include more effective (sector-based) guidance, communication & science education packages and capacity building actions. CHORIZO employs real-life Case Studies (CSs) to serve the above-mentioned purposes.

¹ EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste.

2 SUSTAINABILITY STRATEGY: EU FOOD WASTE ASSOCIATIONS

2.1 Objectives

This sustainability strategy has been developed to establish and maintain strong relationships with FWAs across the EU, with the goal of supporting the dissemination and potential adoption of the CHORIZO project's outcomes including recommendations, tools, and guides aimed at reducing food waste. By engaging directly with these associations, which are already active in this field, the strategy aimed to create collaborative opportunities that amplify the reach and impact of the project. To achieve this, CHORIZO designed a step-by-step roadmap that provides a structured and actionable approach, fostering cooperation, and encouraging the use of project resources within their networks.

The roadmap is designed to:

- 1. Gain a comprehensive understanding of the FWA landscape across the EU.**
Identify key actors involved in food waste prevention and understand their roles, priorities, and potential alignment with the CHORIZO project.
- 2. Promote the long-term sustainability and scaling of CHORIZO's outputs.**
Ensure that the project's tools, guides, and recommendations continue to deliver value beyond the project's timeline by embedding them into the ongoing work of FWAs.
- 3. Building Partnerships with Food Waste Associations.**
Establish contact with selected associations and build partnerships that facilitate knowledge exchange and joint initiatives.
- 4. Support the promotion and practical application of project results during implementation.**
Work with FWAs to actively share and use CHORIZO's materials—such as guides and behavioural tools—within their networks, engaging both consumers and businesses.
- 5. Monitor Engagement and Impact.**
Track the outcomes of these interactions, monitoring how the shared resources are being adopted.

These objectives reflect CHORIZO's commitment to fostering meaningful engagement with food waste associations across the EU. By clearly defining the aims of this strategy, the deliverable sets the foundation for a structured and collaborative effort to ensure the project's outcomes are effectively communicated, adopted, and tailored to support long-term food waste reduction efforts.

2.2 Roadmap overview

To engage effectively with FWAs across the EU, CHORIZO outlines a structured five-step roadmap that supports strategic collaboration and spread the project's outputs. This approach is designed not only to establish partnerships but also to ensure that the tools, recommendations, and behavioural insights developed throughout the project are meaningfully integrated into the work of relevant stakeholders across the FLW chain.

The process begins with **Analysing the current environment**, which involves identifying and mapping existing FWAs operating at both EU and national levels. This step requires a systematic exploration of organizations actively working to reduce food waste, including initiatives focused on awareness campaigns, research, policy advocacy, and private-sector engagement. Also national organisms in charge of FW initiatives at a country level are taken into account. Once identified, associations are classified into five categories: 1) EU initiatives, 2) non-governmental organizations (NGOs), 3) industry alliances, and 4) research institutes, 5) national authorities. This categorization enables a tailored engagement strategy that respects the different roles, target audiences, and operational models of each group.

The second step is the **definition of key recommendations to share**. Drawing from the project’s findings, CHORIZO consolidates a set of evidence-based, action-oriented recommendations aimed at reducing food waste at the consumer and business levels. These are collected and framed to be adaptable to different contexts, ensuring relevance across sectors. The outputs shared include communication products, intervention action, behavioural change tools, and best practices that can be translated into the communication and training efforts of FWAs.

As third step, the **Collaboration and interaction** is crucial, focused on building relationships with selected FWAs. Initial contact is made through personalized outreach—emails, social media, and through FIAB network introductions—followed by B2B meetings to present the project and explore areas of mutual interest. This stage is crucial for fostering trust, understanding the needs and capacities of each organization, and identifying potential areas for synergies. The objective is not only to inform, but to invite FWAs to become active partners in shaping how project outputs are used and disseminated.

The fourth step is **implementation**, where engaged associations are encouraged to incorporate CHORIZO’s outputs into their ongoing work or share the information with their members or other projects related. This may include distributing behavioural change tools through their communication channels, embedding recommendations in training programs, or adapting project materials for use in local or sector-specific contexts. By leveraging the reach and credibility of FWAs, this phase ensures the project’s results extend beyond its immediate network and into practical, real-world application.

Finally, the last step is **monitoring**. This phase supports the long-term sustainability and relevance of the engagement strategy. It involves tracking the uptake of shared tools and recommendations, gathering feedback from associations, and assessing the effectiveness of the collaborations. This step allows the CHORIZO team to adapt materials as needed and ensures that FWA needs and evolving priorities remain central to the project’s dissemination approach.

Figure 1 Roadmap

Altogether, this roadmap represents a scalable and adaptive engagement model that aligns with CHORIZO’s broader mission: to catalyse systemic change in food waste behaviours across Europe by empowering FWAs as key multipliers within the EU food system.

2.3 Timeline

Steps	Timeline	Key Milestones	
Step 1: Mapping and analysing	M25-M36	Map existing associations and analyse the current environment.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) EU initiatives 2) Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) 3) Industry alliances 4) Research institutes 5) National Authorities
Step 2: Definition of outputs	M26-M28	Define the correct outputs to share with FWAs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sector-specific Guidance - Datahub - FLW Rapid Appraisal Tool - Capacity Building - Practice Abstracts (CSs) - Evaluation of 395 Interventions - Communication and education products (different contexts) - Policy Recommendations
Step 3: Collaboration	M28-M31	Contact EU FWAs, establish relations and share interests.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub - Environment Committee of FoodDrinkEurope - EIP-AGRI Project Database - EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste (FLW) - ICLEI – Local Governments for Sustainability - FIAB – Spanish Industry Federation - Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPA) - The Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food in Slovenia (MKGP)
Step 4: Implementation	M32-M35	Share CHORIZO outputs with their network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Working Group meeting with associated partners - Newsletter - Website - Database - Webinars - Press Release/Media - Workshop
Step 5: Monitoring	M36	Monitor the impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - B2B meetings - Network websites that uploaded project content can be tracked - DataHub or the Appraisal Tool, feedback can be collected through the survey - Social media interactions

Table 1 Roadmap and timeline

*The times indicated in the table are tentative.

3 STEP 1: ANALYZING THE CURRENT ENVIRONMENT

This step requires systematic exploration of organizations actively working to reduce food waste. Mapping the landscape of food loss and waste (FLW) associations across the European Union reveals a diverse array of organizations dedicated to mitigating this pressing issue.

Below is a categorized overview of key entities, including EU initiatives, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), industry alliances, research institutes and national organisms.

3.1 European Union Initiatives

3.1.1 EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste (FLW)

Established in 2016, the Platform brings together EU institutions, national authorities, international organizations, and stakeholders from across the food supply chain, the Platform serves as a forum for collaboration, knowledge exchange, development of practical measures to address food waste, shares best practices, and evaluates progress in preventing food waste. Closely aligned with the EU Farm to Fork Strategy.

Their main functions and activities of the Platform are:

- Bringing together a wide range of actors involved in the food value chain.
- Sharing best practices and policy recommendations.
- Defining measures needed to prevent food waste.
- Monitoring and evaluating progress toward FW reduction goals.
- Working through thematic sub-groups (specialised groups) focusing on specific topics.

By engaging with this Platform, the CHORIZO project objective was to align with established EU priorities, contribute to expert dialogue, and ensure its outputs reflect the needs and expectations of the broader European agenda on food waste reduction.

3.1.2 EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub

It's a centralized digital platform launched by the European Commission on 2021. Serves as a "one-stop-shop," the Hub aims to foster collaboration among stakeholders across the EU and beyond who are actively engaged in combating food loss and waste. Their list of Stakeholders includes public authorities, NGOs, businesses, and individuals. The Hub also incorporates content from the REFRESH Community of Experts, ensuring continuity in the dissemination of food waste prevention initiatives.

The Hub is designed to provide several services and resources to its users:

1. Resource sharing/good practices
2. Information on national policies and legislative developments
3. Updates on EU-funded projects
4. News & developments
5. Community/membership component
6. Free accessible content

3.1.3 The European Environmental Bureau

The **European Environmental Bureau (EEB)** is the largest network of environmental citizens' organisations in Europe, bringing together around 180 member organisations from over 40 countries and representing millions of supporters. It works to promote sustainable development, environmental justice and participatory democracy, and is a key actor in shaping and monitoring EU environmental policies. The EEB has a strong focus on circular economy and waste, coordinating working groups on waste prevention, reuse, recycling and product policy, and it plays an important role in the European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform. Through its collaboration with specialised NGOs such as **Feedback EU**, particularly on food waste reduction, the EEB amplifies calls for ambitious EU action, including legally binding targets, and provides a good channel to disseminate project results to policymakers, member organisations and other relevant stakeholders across Europe.

3.1.4 EIP-AGRI Project Database

Optimising the flow of information about agriculture and rural policy within the EU is what the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Network. Maybe upload something else apart from PAs.

The **EIP-AGRI Project Database**, part of the EU CAP Network, is a publicly accessible repository of innovative agriculture, forestry, and rural development projects from across Europe, including *Operational Groups* under CAP (Common Agricultural Policy), Horizon multi-actor research projects, thematic & advisory networks, and other innovation-driven projects.

Projects registered include those that bring together farmers, researchers, advisors, NGOs and businesses, seeking to co-create and apply practical solutions via the "interactive innovation" model.

As part of the EU CAP Network's Innovation & Knowledge Exchange support facility, EIP-AGRI also organizes networking, focus groups, workshops, cross-visits and thematic events to connect stakeholders, identify synergies, feed practice needs into research agendas, and accelerate the diffusion of innovations across rural and agricultural systems in the EU. The database also uses "practice abstracts" in a common EIP-AGRI format so that lessons and outputs from projects are shared in a concise, usable way, which supports uptake and dissemination.

3.2 Non-governmental organizations (NGOs)

3.2.1 Feedback EU

Feedback EU is an environmental organization that campaigns to end food waste across the entire food system, from production to consumption, making it a strategic point for sharing project results and engaging stakeholders interested in sustainable food management.

3.2.2 Slow Food Europe

Slow Food Europe, part of the global Slow Food movement, believes that in a world where millions are undernourished and resources are limited, reducing food waste is essential to achieving a sustainable food system. The organization emphasizes the importance of good, clean, and fair food, and actively advocates against food waste through a variety of initiatives, making it a potential partner for disseminating project results and raising awareness among stakeholders committed to sustainable and equitable food practices.

3.3 Industry Alliances

3.3.1 FoodDrinkEurope

FoodDrinkEurope represents Europe's food and drink industry and runs initiatives aimed at reducing food waste across the entire supply chain. Through the regular meetings of its **Environment Committee**, they constitute a strong channel to disseminate project results in front of relevant representatives from the food industry across Europe, adapting the outputs to their specific interests.

3.3.2 European Federation of Food Banks (FEBA)

The **European Federation of Food Banks (FEBA)** is a network of food banks across Europe that works to reduce hunger and food waste by redistributing surplus food to those in need, making it an important partner for sharing project results with organizations directly engaged in practical food waste reduction and social impact initiatives. Through our partner **HFBA**, it is possible to establish direct communication effectively.

3.3.3 The Association of Manufacturers and Retailers (AECOC)

AECOC is one of Spain's leading business associations, bringing together manufacturers and retailers across the food value chain. Through its **Committee Against Food Waste**, AECOC promotes collaborative initiatives, awareness campaigns, and practical measures to reduce food waste in Spain.

3.4 National Authorities (Policy makers)

3.4.1 Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food in Spain

The **Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPA) in Spain** can be considered a key dissemination body for food waste content due to its active involvement in national programs and initiatives aimed at preventing and reducing food waste. As the governmental authority overseeing agricultural production, food policy, and distribution, MAPA has both the mandate and the network to reach relevant stakeholders across the food chain, including producers, distributors, retailers, and consumers, ensuring that project results and best practices can be effectively shared and promoted at a national level.

3.4.2 Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food in Slovenia

The **Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food in Slovenia** can likewise be considered an important dissemination body for food waste content due to its active role in national programs and initiatives aimed at preventing and reducing food waste. As the governmental authority responsible for agriculture, food policy, and the national food system, it has the mandate and network to reach key stakeholders across the food chain, including producers, distributors, retailers, and consumers, allowing project results and best practices to be effectively communicated and promoted at a national level.

4 STEP 2: DEFINITION OF RECOMMENDATIONS TO SHARE

2. Definition of recommendations to share
 Define clear recommendations for reducing food waste across the EU.

Key insights and data from the CHORIZO project were shared with a wide range of organizations. These resources include key findings from interviews, datasets, guides or recommendations, communication products, and analytical tools relevant to surplus food management. Depending on the specific challenges each organization aims to address, we provided tailored access to additional materials from the CHORIZO Datahub. This ensures that all shared content is contextually relevant and actionable.

The CHORIZO Datahub, hosted at <https://data.chorizoproject.eu/>, functions as an open-access platform where various types of data and analytical tools are made available:

- Qualitative interview data: In-depth interviews with stakeholders from different contexts.
- Structured datasets: with open access.
- Analytical tools and visualizations.
- Reports and best practices.
- User-friendly guides.

Figure 2 Different topics of data in the Datahub

These resources can provide critical support for:

- Improving organizational decision-making on surplus food redistribution.
- Understanding consumer and institutional behaviors related to food waste.
- Designing evidence-based interventions and advocacy strategies.

Depending on the specific focus area of each organization, additional, targeted resources can be used. The CHORIZO Datahub supports a diverse range of initiatives, whether it's the FWAs working on food redistribution, food banks optimizing surplus management, industry alliances improving sector-wide practices, or research institutes advancing academic knowledge and policy recommendations.

4.1 Key Recommendations and Target Audiences

4.1.1 For NGOs and Civil Society Organizations (e.g. Feedback EU, Slow Food Europe, FEBA)

Main recommendations

- Integrate behavioural insights into awareness campaigns and advocacy strategies.
- Use project guides and communication packages to strengthen citizen-facing initiatives.
- Leverage CHORIZO evidence to advocate for ambitious national and EU-level food waste reduction targets.

Main tools and outputs

- Behavioural Change Guides → for designing campaigns that influence household and consumer practices.
- Capacity Building Programme → training for staff and volunteers on applying social norms to food waste prevention.
- Comparative Evaluation of 395 Interventions → evidence base to select effective interventions for their advocacy work.

4.1.2 For Industry Alliances and Business Associations (e.g. FoodDrinkEurope, FIAB, sector federations)

Main recommendations

- Embed CHORIZO outputs into industry guidelines and sustainability strategies.
- Share sector-adapted recommendations with company members through committees and working groups.
- Encourage members to apply behavioural tools internally to reduce operational food waste and engage consumers.

Main tools and outputs

- CHORIZO DataHub → structured datasets and visualisations to inform company decision-making.
- “Insighter” Status Report → sector-focused evidence and benchmarking for industry sustainability reports.
- Practice Abstracts → concise summaries tailored for different communities.

4.1.3 For National Authorities and Policy Makers (e.g. MAPA in Spain, Ministry of Agriculture in Slovenia)

Main recommendations

- Integrate CHORIZO findings into national strategies, legislation, and monitoring frameworks.
- Use outputs to train regional/local authorities and improve coordination with municipalities.
- Promote adoption of tested interventions through public awareness programmes and policies.

Main tools and outputs

- Policy-Oriented Recommendations → high-level proposals derived from project insights.
- Capacity Building Events → support for training civil servants and local policymakers.
- Comparative Evaluation of Interventions → evidence to design policies grounded in proven effectiveness.

4.1.4 For Research and Knowledge Networks (e.g. EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub, EIP-AGRI Project Database, ICLEI)

Main recommendations

- Disseminate CHORIZO outputs within their networks to facilitate cross-project learning.
- Use results to support joint initiatives and feed evidence into new EU-funded projects.
- Maintain the long-term accessibility of CHORIZO resources through databases and hubs.

Main tools and outputs

- CHORIZO DataHub → open-access platform for data, analytical tools, and case studies.
- Practice Abstracts → concise knowledge products to support agricultural and rural innovation.
- CIG Webinars (ICLEI) → recordings and materials to engage municipalities and local governments.

By making these resources widely accessible, we aim to empower these organizations to take informed, data-driven actions that enhance their efforts in reducing food loss and waste, ultimately strengthening the impact of EU policies and industry collaborations.

5 STEPS 3 & 4: COLLABORATION OR INTERACTION, AND IMPLEMENTATION

Collaboration and interaction with Food Waste Associations (FWAs) have been an essential component of the CHORIZO dissemination strategy, with the objective of fostering knowledge exchange, building relationships, and supporting joint initiatives. These efforts ensured that the project's outputs reached a wide range of stakeholders and were integrated into existing European and national platforms dedicated to food waste prevention.

The implementation of these results depends on the nature of each organisation, taking place through different channels such as sharing with partners or committee members, uploading content directly to their websites, or simply including it in their databases for future use when needed.

The following FWAs and institutions were actively engaged and adopted CHORIZO results:

- **EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub:** Direct communication with the network managers and submission of several resources in month 12, month 20, month 32 and month 33, including [the CHORIZO capacity building programme on applying social norms to food waste solutions, solutions for city actors, the comparative evaluation of 395 interventions, the Datahub and "Insighter" Status Report](#), and outputs from the [joint CHORIZO–ZeroW multi-stakeholder conference](#). This Food Waste Association was selected as the main platform to share the project's results, which have also reached members of other EU projects as well as relevant stakeholders.
- **Environment Committee of FoodDrinkEurope:** Presentation of the full project scope and DATAHUB, Practice Abstracts and Sector-specific Guidance during their periodic committee meetings (month 32) with representatives of the European food and drink industry thanks to Katrin Heeren, Director Environment & Sustainability at FDE. Presentation of results in the RDI Working Group thanks to Rebeca Fernandez, Director Food Safety, Research & Innovation (month 25 and 27). Through these Committees and Working Groups, Europe's food and drink manufacturers provide broad and in-depth expertise.
- **EIP-AGRI Project Database:** The EIP-AGRI network is highly relevant for interaction with other projects, as it facilitates connections, knowledge exchange, and collaboration across the European agricultural and rural innovation community. Our main contact was Sarah Beigel, Communication manager at the European CAP Network. The practice Abstracts were shared with her and upload together with complete project information, in [the EU CAP Network](#). Through this Practice Abstracts model, we were able to disseminate the project outputs via their network, which also helped us connect with other initiatives that discovered us through the website. **EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste (FLW):** Sharing of multiple materials (Practice Abstracts with CS results, DataHub, Sector-specific Guidance) from month 25 to month 33 to be shared with their stakeholders. The contact has been done through different meetings with their members, such as FoodDrinkEurope, AZTI technological center and COPA COGECA.
- **ICLEI – Local Governments for Sustainability:** As a project partner, ICLEI integrated CHORIZO results into its sustainability strategy by disseminating all CIG webinars to its network of European cities. Results shared include FLW Rapid Appraisal Tool, Communication Products, DataHub, Capacity Building.

- **FIAB – Spanish Industry Federation:** as project partner integrated CHORIZO results sharing sector-adapted recommendations, the DataHub and the Rapid Appraisal Tool through 45 industry associations via internal communication with associations and through Press Releases with relevant impact on media, reaching a wider scope including technological centres, general public and policy makers.
- **The Association of Manufacturers and Retailers (AECOC):** Thanks to Carolina Muro, President of AECOC’s Committee Against Food Waste, we were able to share the link to access the DataHub, the Practice Abstracts, and the sector-specific guidance with the members of that committee.
- **Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPA):** Participation in national events where the project and its industry-related results in Spain were presented and discussed with relevant policy makers from the Spanish Ministry, highly involved in Food Waste initiatives at a National level. María Paz Santamaría, Head of Service Sub-Directorate General for Food Quality and Sustainability at the Spanish Ministry participated in the workshop celebrated in Madrid (June 2023), where she shared her point of view and took notes for future recommendations. The Ministry also expressed interest in the project outputs after FIAB Press Release for the Final Conference (September 2025). Leticia Copano, Head of Service Sub- Directorate General for Food Quality and Sustainability, as participant in FIAB Food Waste Working Group, asked for detailed information on the DataHub, Appraisal Tool, Practice Abstracts and Capacity Building programme.
- **The Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food in Slovenia (MKGP):** The Ministry expressed appreciation for the Sector-specific Guidance to guide its members to better decision-making, noting that it contains many useful ideas relevant to the Slovenian context, particularly for collaboration with municipalities. The Ministry asked about the availability of a Slovenian version, indicating their willingness to publish it on their website. Furthermore, they recommended actively promoting the recommendations to local mayors, the Chamber of Craft and Small Business, and the Chamber of Agriculture and Forestry, including the presentation of concrete examples of potential collaboration and actions.

6 STEP 5: MONITORING

To ensure the long-term effectiveness of the strategy, it is essential to monitor how food waste associations engage with the project's resources and to evaluate the results of these interactions, this step consists of understanding whether these collaborations are truly adding value and helping the project meet their goals by establishing mechanisms to track uptake, usage, and dissemination of CHORIZO's tools, guides, and recommendations across FWA networks. A lightweight, low-maintenance monitoring strategy is followed that aligns with the available resources.

The aim is to track both the usage of the tools and the extent to which they are being shared, cited, or embedded into relevant practices or policies.

The monitoring strategy is implemented through **B2B meetings** with those stakeholders with whom direct contact is maintained, such as FoodDrinkEurope and national Ministries. In addition, interaction on the network websites that uploaded project **content can be tracked**, analysing the level of interest generated by the shared results. Finally, for those entities that used the DataHub or the Appraisal Tool, **feedback can be collected** through the survey designed by the teams responsible for these tools.

Social media visibility often reflects both dissemination and endorsement by relevant organisations and networks, to get to know this mentions or shares of project tools and outputs on official CHORIZO social channels pages. This monitoring strategy relies on the analysis of interaction on social media channels.

The indicators above provide a clear, evidence-based picture of how the CHORIZO outputs are being used, shared, and received by external organisations.

To ensure the long-term exploitation of results beyond the project's lifetime, the CHORIZO website will remain active and accessible for five additional years after project completion, hosting all key outputs such as the DataHub, Practice Abstracts, sector-specific guidance, the Rapid Appraisal Tool and reports. This continued availability will allow Food Waste Associations (FWAs) and other stakeholders to access, use, and integrate the resources into their ongoing activities. By embedding CHORIZO's tools within established FWA networks and ensuring open access to project results, the strategy provides both the capacity and incentive for FWAs to maintain engagement and apply the recommendations in their programmes, policies, and industry practices well beyond M36.

7 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the sustainability strategy developed for engagement with EU Food Waste Associations ensures that CHORIZO's project outcomes (tools, guides, and recommendations) achieve lasting impact beyond the project's duration. By mapping the FWA landscape, establishing targeted partnerships, and promoting the practical use of project resources within these networks, the strategy creates a structured framework for continuous dissemination and adoption. The step-by-step roadmap not only facilitates cooperation and knowledge exchange but also supports the long-term scaling of CHORIZO outputs, embedding them into the ongoing work of associations active in food waste prevention. Through regular monitoring of engagement and impact, the project can track the effectiveness of these interactions and adapt its approach as needed, ensuring that CHORIZO contributes meaningfully to reducing food waste among both consumers and businesses across the EU. This approach demonstrates a sustainable and replicable model for leveraging existing networks to maximize the project's reach, uptake, and long-term benefits.

CHORIZO PROJECT

